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What children think about engineering: Children's perceptions of engineering following participation in an engineering education activity.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Since the publication of the Roberts' Review in 2002 [1] there has been an increased focus on STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) education in the UK, as summarised by Hoyle [2]. With the UK Government and Engineering Professional Bodies calling for increased STEM education focused at Secondary level and above [3], an industry around STEM education provision has emerged within the UK, leading to the ad-hoc provision of engineering education within compulsory education. The outcomes of this provision are now being questioned [2, 4]; evaluations of the current provision of engineering education are sparse [5] and have tended to

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focus on the 11+ age group, and inner city schools [6]. Recent literature has also suggested that children may be eliminating STEM careers during Primary school [7].

This paper presents part of a PhD study aimed at increasing our understanding of the outcomes of participation in an Engineering Education Activity (EEA) for Primary school children in rural schools. Thus helping to develop our understanding of the role that the current provision of engineering education plays at this age, an area that is relatively unexplored within the literature yet has significant consequences for the future of engineering [4].

2 METHODOLOGY

The current study posed the question:

How does participation in an Engineering Education Activity in Year 5 (age 9/10 in England) affect children's perceptions of engineering as a career at Year 7 (age 11/12 in England)?

In order to answer this question the study took a longitudinal, qualitative approach, utilising a case study methodology, drawing on grounded theory to inform the data collection and analysis process, as described by Broadbent [8].

Exploration of the children's perceptions of engineering and experience of participation in an EEA was obtained from the first person perspective, using exploratory observations and group interviews. Fieldwork was carried out with children from two schools over three school years, Year 5 to Year 7. This paper presents the findings relating to the perceptions of engineering held by the children following participation in an EEA at school.

The school ethics committee at Aston University granted ethical approval for this study and an ethical approach was maintained throughout the work, as discussed by Broadbent [8].

3 FIELDWORK

Data was collected between January 2016 and December 2017, from children at two rural Staffordshire schools (details of which are provided in *Table 1*), known in this work as Nant School and Phren School.

Table 1. Summary of information about the two research cases

	Nant School	Phren School
Type of school	Primary School Reception – Year 6 (age 4-11)	Middle School Year 5 – Year 8 (age 9-13)
Number of children enrolled (2016/17)	120	419
Number of participants	19 (12 males, 7 females) Predominantly White British with English as their first language.	29 (15 males, 14 females) Predominantly White British with English as their first language.

The EEA at Nant School formed part of the Design Technology curriculum taught at the school and was delivered by the class teacher. The activity took place in the Year 5 classroom over multiple lessons, two of which were observed as part of this research. The activity involved researching, designing, and building a simple moving toy.

The EEA at Phren School was an off-timetable, curriculum enrichment activity delivered by an external provider. The activity took place in the main hall of the school, the children participated in the activity in their tutor groups, and each session lasted between 45 minutes and 1 hour. The activity focused on the children building and testing a balloon powered car.

Exploratory observations were conducted in each case, observing the children participating in the EEA in order to inform the interviews and subsequent analysis of the data. Semi-structured, group interviews with the children were carried out three times during the research, once in Year 5 (0-1 months post EEA), once in Year 6 (6-12 months post EEA), and once in Year 7 (18-24 months post EEA). The findings from the interview data concerning the children's perceptions of engineering are presented in this paper.

4 FINDINGS

The interview data is presented in the dominant themes that emerged during the collection and initial stage of analysis. To illustrate the findings quotes are given; all are in italics and are accompanied by the gender, school year, and case of the child to whom the quote is attributed, given in parenthesis directly beneath the quote.

4.1 Perceptions of Engineering

The majority of the children interviewed in Year 5 held perceptions about engineering, with two dominant categories appearing in both cases. From Year 5 to Year 7, the children's perceptions of engineering were chiefly either product-focused (referring to specific artefacts the child associated with engineering) or process-focused (referring to specific practices the child associated with engineering).

It's like designing, it's not like, I don't think you do like the building it is just like designing, ideas and machinery.

(M, Year 5, Phren School)

Isn't it fixing things and is it a lot, don't you need to be really good at maths to do it?

(F, Year 7, Nant School)

Within the product-focused perceptions of engineering, transport was frequently cited as the artefact the children associated with engineering.

...for example you could engineer a car or a train or a plane.

(M, Year 5, Phren School)

Very few children appeared to hold perceptions divergent to these categories, however a small minority of children at each stage held perceptions of engineering in terms of the impact that engineering has on the world.

They help the world move on to like high tech stuff.

(M, Year 5, Nant School)

The majority of the children did not refer to the EEA without prompting when talking about engineering at any stage of the research, indicating that the perceptions they held about engineering formed prior to participation in the EEA. When this area was explored in the interviews the children spoke of a range of sources that informed them, with formal engineering education not appearing to factor in the formation of their perceptions about engineering.

4.2 Recall of activity

During each interview the children were asked to recall the EEA they had participated in, initially questions focused on the children's recall of the activity itself and then progressed to talking about the engineering involved in the activity.

Although many of the children had limited recollections of the activity in Year 6 and Year 7, the use of photographs taken during the EEA enabled the children to speak about their participation. Only a minority of the children referred to the activity as engineering without prompt questions introducing this area of discussion. When this did occur, the children largely stated that the activity was an engineering activity, or spoke about being told that the activity was engineering.

Yeah the toys one they said it was engineering...

(M, Year 6, Nant School)

It was a STEM activity.

(M, Year 7, Phren School)

When the interviewer used questions to explore these statements, many of the children were unable to expand on these assertions. However, once the topic was raised, children who had not identified the activity as engineering began to draw links between the EEA and engineering; some talked about the similarities and others the differences, with the responses focusing on the children's appraisal of the artefacts and processes involved in the EEA.

It's not like actually engineering, like a proper car or something like that.

(M, Year 5, Nant School)

Cos you were building it wasn't you, you were trying to find a way to build it.

(M, Year 7, Phren School)

A minority of children exhibited a different perspective and spoke about the engineering content of the activity in terms of whether they felt they had experienced

doing the work of an engineer when participating in the EEA, and the concept of *proper engineering* emerged within a number of the children's narratives.

It isn't like what you would do for engineering so you wouldn't actually know like what you would do for engineering, so that hasn't really helped because it isn't proper engineering.

(F, Year 6, Phren School)

Although the above quote indicates a lack of bearing on perceptions, a small minority of children during the Year 6 and Year 7 interviews spoke about areas where they felt participation in the EEA had influenced their perceptions. These changes focused on a number of different areas, the principal focus was a shift in the perceived difficulty of engineering, with children finding that the EEA was more challenging than they had thought it would be.

I thought "Oh it looks very easy" and you just put all the stuff together but it's actually really hard.

(F, Year 6, Nant School)

For a minority of the children, participation appeared to change perceptions around the processes involved in engineering. This occurred within both cases, however noticeably the change in perceptions for some children at Phren School, were limited to changes within their existing perception framework. This was observed where children expanded their ideas about engineering processes whilst the product they associated with engineering remained constant.

I didn't realise that they had to go through many stages to get it built, like planning and designing.

(F, Year 6, Nant School)

I used to think that engineering was just like they were people who just like went around and fixed cars, I didn't know that they actually made them, it made me think that they actually made them.

(M, Year 7, Phren School)

Whilst the majority of children identified no change in perceptions, or limited and minor alterations in their perceptions of engineering as described above, there were two notable exceptions. Firstly were the very small minority of children who identified the activity as their introduction to engineering and a nucleus of interest and knowledge acquisition; participation in the EEA appeared to provide some children with interest and the vocabulary they needed to find out more about engineering. For some however, this inspiration was seen to have dissipated by Year 7.

Since we learnt about this and this was called engineering we started watching more things on engineering because we thought it was cool...

(M, Year 6, Nant School)

In Year 5 it made me more interested [in engineering] and then through Year 6 I was still but I sort of am now, but not as much.

(M, Year 7, Phren School)

Secondly, a minority of the girls at Phren School spoke of their gendered-views of engineering ability being challenged by participation in the activity.

I think that I thought the boys were gonna be all really good at it but some, like the girls were good at it as well.

(F, Year 6, Phren School)

As the children did not explicitly gender engineering as a career, this finding suggests that for some children an implicit assumption about the engineering abilities of girls and boys may exist at a young age. Whilst these findings indicate that the EEA may inform perceptions for a small number of children in the year following participation, reflections by the children during the Year 7 interviews suggest that participation in the EEA during Year 5 did not inform the perceptions of engineering held by the majority of the children in either case in the long term.

Not really. It was kind of like, I've already done that kind of thing before.

(M, Year 7, Nant School)

I don't really think about it [engineering] and I've never really been like told what it is properly so I haven't really ever like thought about it because I don't really know what it is.

(F, Year 7, Phren School)

5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The data from the Year 5 interviews illustrated that the children formed perceptions about engineering prior to engaging in formal engineering education. The data also highlighted the prominence of product-focused and process-focused perceptions held by children at this age, with an emphasis on transport and fixing. Although there is a limited volume of research in this area, these findings are found to be congruent with existing findings in the UK [9]. When examined in relation to the existing definitions of engineering provided by the profession (for example [10]) it can be seen that by focusing on a limited number of artefacts or processes, the children hold narrow views of engineering. This focus on specific roles within engineering, for example designing cars, results in the children holding inaccurate views of what engineering involves, as they miss the holistic definition of engineering as a creative, problem-solving profession that contributes to society [10].

The children's perceptions are seen to persist from Year 5 to Year 7, indicating that participation in an EEA in Year 5 does not result in children holding accurate perceptions of engineering, and that participation in an EEA in Year 5 does not significantly alter a child's existing perceptions of engineering. A notable exception to this was the concept of ability, where changes in perceived difficulty of engineering and gendered ability were visible for a minority of children; participation in the EEA

enabled some children to evaluate the challenging nature of engineering, and enabled some girls to see boys and girls as equally able. This indicates that attention needs to be paid to the structure of EEAs in order to capitalise on the potential that these activities have to inform children's perceptions regarding ability.

In order to understand the outcomes of participation in an EEA on the children's perceptions, analysis of how the children spoke about the engineering content they perceived the activity to contain was carried out. For the majority of the children, participation in the EEA did not appear to challenge their existing perceptions of engineering, resulting in the majority of children using their existing perceptions of engineering to inform their experience of the activity. This was observed as the children tended to use their perceived product or process lens to view the engineering involved in the EEA. This appeared to lead to the reinforcement of existing, narrow perceptions, for those children who could align the EEA to their perceptions of engineering, and the feeling that an experience of engineering had not been gained for those children whose perceptions differed from the content of EEA.

The outcome of this finding is significant, implying that for some children their existing perceptions went unaltered, with some dismissing the EEA as not engineering and therefore not using the experience to inform their perceptions regarding engineering. However, for some the inaccurate perceptions of engineering that were held prior to participation in the EEA may be reinforced by participation. This was seen in the case of Phren School more dominantly than Nant School, and concerned the focus of the EEA (building a balloon car). This finding indicates that the product of a 'design-and-build' EEA influences the outcomes of participation; although neither EEA appeared to challenge or improve the narrow perceptions held by the children, it is possible that having an EEA focused on an engineering artefact which children already associate with engineering, reinforces narrow perceptions.

It is argued that whilst EEAs during Primary school appear to have the potential to alter perceptions regarding gender and engineering ability, current provision appears to have little impact on the narrow perceptions of engineering as a field held by children; at best they appear to leave these perceptions unaltered, at worst they appear to reinforce them. The significance of the accuracy of the perceptions held by the children is illustrated when considering in context with the other findings of this research, which suggest that the children use their perceptions to create personal definitions of what "*proper engineering*" entails and that these are then used to evaluate subsequent interactions with engineering education.

The findings of this research suggest that in order to develop engineering education that equips future generations with accurate definitions of engineering, enabling them to make informed decisions regarding engineering careers, a deeper understanding of the formation of engineering perceptions is needed, as well as a critical evaluation of pedagogical approaches employed in EEAs. The aim of these enquiries should be to understand the role that other areas of society play in the formation of perceptions of engineering for young children, as well as ensuring that activities provide accurate portrayals of engineering that are internalised by the participating children.

6 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper presents part of the findings from a PhD study exploring the outcomes of participation in an Engineering Education Activity for children during Primary school. The findings of this research indicate that although a minority of

children gain an increased awareness of engineering through participation in an EEA, participation in a one-off engineering education activity in Year 5 (age 9/10) does not significantly influence a child's perceptions of engineering over the following two years of education. This study finds that understanding the outcomes of participation in an EEA on the perceptions of engineering held by the children is complex; outcomes appear to be associated with a highly personal process involving comparisons between the activity itself and the child's own perception of engineering. The findings of this research indicate that the current provision of engineering education does not adequately understand, acknowledge, and challenge these existing perceptions. It is argued that without this forming part of an EEA, participation is unlikely to result in an accurate understanding of what engineering entails, with the worst case scenario being that participation reinforces narrow, stereotypical views of engineering. It is concluded that formal engineering education needs to progress from single 'design-and-make' challenges provided sporadically to children, and that without a change in this provision perceptions about engineering will not be challenged and improved to accurately reflect the engineering profession. This research provides an insight into a previously unexplored perspective of engineering education research, which challenges our present understanding of the efficacy of current models of engineering education provision in the UK.

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